

Autonomous SDN-Driven Operations in Disaggregated Open Optical Transport Network with Coherent Pluggable Transceivers: A Demonstration

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Abstract: This demonstration validates autonomous operations of an optical SDN controller to deliver QoT-enabled optical connectivity services, leveraging open control interfaces, real-time telemetry, and effective recovery strategies in a disaggregated, multi-vendor optical transport network. © 2024 The Author(s)

1. Overview

Software-Defined Networking (SDN) principles enable controllers to program and configure heterogeneous, multi-vendor (*disaggregated*) network infrastructures and devices, including transponders with coherent DWDM small-form-factor transceivers (e.g., *pluggables*), amplifiers, and ROADMs. Additionally, SDN controllers increasingly integrate advanced autonomic operations that manage the full lifecycle of optical connectivity services—covering creation, updating, recovery, and termination—by retrieving monitoring and telemetry data [1]. Consequently, the SDN controller can apply *closed-loop* mechanisms to continually ensure service demands are met while autonomously reconfiguring services in response to QoT degradations, network failures, or traffic variations.

Consolidated SDN frameworks revolve around 2 key pillars: (i) functional, modular architectures that offload computation-intensive tasks, e.g., path computation; and (ii) open APIs that combine solid protocol frameworks (e.g., NETCONF, RESTCONF, and gRPC/gNMI) with standard YANG-based data models (OpenConfig and OpenROADM) for terminal devices (transponders) and optical line elements (ROADMs). Following such design guidelines, Fig. 1 depicts the architecture of an autonomous Optical SDN Controller implemented to manage a disaggregated optical transport network in the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed[®]. The infrastructure comprises 2 optical terminals, referred to as Open Transponders (OTs), connected to a core network consisting of 4 ROADMs.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the SDN-Controlled Disaggregated Optical Network with Open Transponders

OTs are based on *whitebox* approach featuring an open Network Operating System (NOS) based on SONiC [2], which supports the configuration of disaggregated (multi-vendor) transponder components, including ASICs and coherent *pluggable* transceivers. Such transceivers, based on 400G QSFP-DD ZR+, support configuring C-band central frequency, output Tx power, and operational modes resulting from diverse symbol rates (30 and 60 Gbauds) and modulation formats (DP-QPSK, DP-8QAM, and DP-16QAM). Thus, OTs can operate at heterogeneous data rates of 100, 200, 300, and 400 Gb/s. On the other hand, ROADMs are designed based on a *route-and-select* architecture, integrating fiber optical switches, arrayed waveguide gratings (AWGs) and Wavelength Selective Switches (WSSs). For a connectivity service between OT1-OT2, the SDN controller selects a feasible path which

includes the list of nodes/links, the operational mode, and the central frequency. Such capabilities/characteristics are programmed by OTs' and ROADMs' agents using a NETCONF API (OpenConfig and OpenROADM data models). Once the service is set up, monitoring and telemetry data from the OTs are streamed to the SDN controller. To do that, the controller firstly subscribes either *periodically* or on an *event-driven* basis. The telemetry data, conveyed through gNMI, includes metrics like received OSNR and PRE-FEC-BER levels. This, in turn, enables the SDN controller to assess any degradation in the connection's Quality of Transmission (QoT). If this occurs, the SDN controller autonomously triggers service reconfiguration. This demonstration showcases the SDN controller's operations and workflows in supporting the entire connectivity lifecycle by effectively interacting with device agents using open APIs to ensure both service demands and required QoT level.

2. Innovation

Autonomous SDN control for connectivity provisioning and recovery, aided by telemetry in disaggregated (multi-vendor) OT and ROADM networks, has gained significant attention in recent years [3][4][5][6]. In [3], Proof-of-Concept demonstrated a Software Agent with gNMI streaming telemetry seamlessly integrated across different NOS implementations (SONiC, Open Network Linux, etc.), enabling SDN controllers to access telemetry such as CPU, memory usage, and transponder metrics (e.g., Tx/Rx Power, PRE-FEC-BER). In a multi-vendor optical transport context, [4] showcased optical service provisioning with physical impairment validation via OpenConfig and TAPI interfaces. For partially disaggregated networks based on SONiC NOS, [5] validated connectivity provisioning using a hierarchical SDN architecture, coordinating Packet and Optical control instances to configure OTs and ROADMs via OpenConfig and OpenROADMs. This was further extended in [6] for automatic recovery of packet flows in IPoWDM infrastructures under fiber/link failures.

Our demonstration introduces key advancements: autonomous service recovery by processing OT telemetry data via gNMI, such as OSNR and/or PRE-FEC-BER levels, allowing the SDN controller to address both service failures and/or QoT degradations; deployment of the NETCONF Agent within Docker containers on the SONiC OS enhancing modularity and simplifying cross-platform management; simplified control relying on a single SDN control for managing both OTs and ROADMs, i.e., removing hierarchical complexity; two recovery strategies: *re-routing* and *updating*. Re-routing, based on *break-before-make* solution, recalculates service connectivity, possibly altering OT configurations and ROADMs. This approach is convenient for *hard* network failures such as fiber cuts. *Updating* adjusts OT configurations (e.g., operational mode) without changing the path, which attains a less disruptive recovery, being interesting for *soft* QoT-degraded services.

3. OFC Relevance

Autonomous control and operations via a centralized SDN controller in disaggregated, multi-vendor optical networks are seen as essential by network operators. Disaggregation offers compelling benefits: enhanced flexibility, eliminating vendor lock-in, enabling more competitive and tailored network infrastructures. It also allows a modular integration approach which decouples the lifecycle of network elements (e.g., OTs) and enables a *pay-as-you-grow* model. However, it introduces challenges, such as increased responsibility for system design and integration and more complex service management. Thus, adopting APIs with well-defined data models, like OpenConfig and OpenROADM, is critical. Moreover, the SDN controller must support closed-loop (*observe-decide-act*) operations through a robust telemetry system, ensuring service quality levels and enabling proactive recovery strategies for hard and soft network failures, as proposed in this demonstration. Consequently, we view OFC as the ideal venue for showcasing this work, given the presence of leading experts from academia and industry, including operators and vendors, who are recognized authorities on the technological challenges addressed in this demonstration.

4. Demonstration Procedure

The autonomous SDN controller demonstrates provisioning and recovery of connectivity services using the workflow in Fig. 2(a) with these steps:

- **Step (1):** Through a Northbound Interface, the Optical SDN controller receives a request (e.g., from a user application via a GUI) for a 100Gb/s connection between OT1 and OT2.
- **Step (2):** The SDN controller runs a Routing, Spectrum, and Modulation Assignment (RSMA) algorithm, selecting the path OT1 → ROADM-4 → ROADM-2 → OT2 with a central frequency of 193.4 THz, slot width of 100 GHz, and operational mode 1 (60 Gbaud, DP-16QAM, yielding 400 Gb/s).
- **Step (3):** OT1 and OT2 are configured via NETCONF/OpenConfig API with the specified frequency, transmission power, and operational mode. That is, the implemented CTTC's NETCONF Agent processes and executes received SDN controller-driven configurations on each OT.

- **Step (4):** ROADM-4 and ROADM-2 are configured via NETCONF/OpenROADM for ingress/egress ports/interfaces, central frequency, and slot width. The received optical signal at OT2 is shown in Fig. 2(c).

Fig. 2. (a) Autonomous SDN control workflow; (b) CTTC GUI: Network Management; (c) Optical signal at RX OT2; (d) Stream telemetry data with PRE-FEC-BER at OT2.

- **Step (5):** The Optical SDN controller subscribes to OT2 telemetry via gNMI API. The gNMI Notification stream is limited to the computed connection's PRE-FEC-BER value, enabling the SDN controller to assess QoT adequacy. The on-change mode triggers notifications whenever PRE-FEC-BER updates.

- **Step (6):** A network anomaly (e.g., adding high-power adjacent channel, coupling a C-band noise) degrades service QoT level.

- **Step (7):** Received PRE-FEC-BER changes, then a gNMI Notification is sent carrying the JSON-encoded contents shown in Fig.2(d), such as timestamp and new measured PRE-FEC-BER.

- **Steps (8) and (9):** To recover a QoT-degraded service, *re-routing* and *updating* strategies are applied. Re-routing selects new path (ROADM-4, ROADM-3, ROADM-2) with OTs at 400 Gb/s. Updating approach retains original path but adjusting OT operational mode to 100 Gb/s (30 Gbaud, DP-QPSK), to improve QoT level.

The demonstration will be visualized by the attendees using the CTTC GUI depicted in Fig. 2 (b). Additionally, for both recovery strategies, it will be shown the time required to complete the service recovery.

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